

Effects of natural disturbances on soil fauna in forests: a systematic map protocol

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Abstract

Background

Natural disturbances to forests such as droughts, storms, fire, and pest outbreaks are likely to increase in frequency and severity as a result of anthropogenic climate change. The effects of these disturbances on tree mortality, forest structure, and aboveground biodiversity are relatively well understood and multiple meta-analyses have characterised this. However, our understanding of the effects of these disturbances on belowground biodiversity is limited, particularly for soil fauna. To address this we will undertake a systematic map to characterise the evidence base for the effects of natural disturbances in forests on soil fauna. As part of this we aim to identify knowledge clusters that could be synthesised using systematic review and knowledge gaps that warrant new primary studies.

Methods

Searches will be carried out in English and using bibliographic platforms (Scopus, Web of Science Core Collection, and Open Access Theses and Dissertations) and internet searches (Google Scholar). Our search terms are defined by the PECO elements of our research questions and aim to identify studies that are carried out in forests investigating the impacts of drought, rainfall increases, windthrow, fire, insect pests, or tree pathogens on soil biodiversity. We will screen publications in three stages: (1) using titles (2) using abstracts and (3) using full texts. At title and abstract stage all texts will be screened using the online platform sysrev. Consistency of inclusion will be checked by two people screening a random sample of 10% of titles and abstracts. This dual-screening will be subject to kappa analysis to check consistency and any disagreements resolved through discussion. Data extraction

from studies will include: Geographic location, timing of studies, duration of studies, disturbance type, maximum time after disturbance, taxa studied, functional group studied, outcomes measured, study design, type of temporal sampling, sampling methods, analytical methods, and the availability of data. Results will be presented to summarise characteristics of the dataset, such as the frequency of studies from different regions, different disturbances, focal taxonomic groups, study outcomes, and other relevant characteristics. We will generate heat maps to show if these characteristics co-occur and use narrative synthesis to discuss themes found in the literature.

Background

Anthropogenic climate change has led to an increase in the likelihood of extreme weather events such as droughts and storms. As a consequence of these changes in climate, the frequency of other perturbations to forests such as fire (Pechony & Shindell 2010), insect pest outbreaks (Ju *et al.* 2015), and plant pathogen outbreaks have also increased (Sturrock *et al.* 2011). These disturbances can have major impacts on tree growth and mortality (Jacquet, Orazio & Jactel 2012) and consequently on carbon stored in plant biomass (Zvereva, Lanta & Kozlov 2010; Wang *et al.* 2021) as well as aboveground biodiversity (Gibson *et al.* 2011). These unprecedented changes represent a major challenge for current and future forest management.

Although the impacts of these different natural disturbances on forest structure and aboveground biodiversity are relatively well understood, this is not true for belowground biodiversity. This lack of understanding is problematic because of the importance of soil biodiversity in regulating multiple ecosystem functions in forests such as the organic matter decomposition (Handa *et al.* 2014) and nutrient cycling (Nielsen, Wall & Six 2015). These processes play a role in determining carbon storage - which in the context of forests is particularly relevant due to their major roles as carbon sinks. In order to inform predictions of how changes in the frequency and severity of natural forest disturbances might affect forest soil processes it is vital to determine their impacts on soil organisms. However, there have been few syntheses of the impacts of natural disturbances on soil biodiversity, and those that exist predominantly focus on impacts on soil microbes (Dooley & Treseder 2012; Abbasi *et al.* 2020; Zhou, Wang & Luo 2020, but see Pressler, Moore, and Catrufo, 2019). As such we lack a general understanding of the effects of natural forest disturbances on soil fauna, and how effects might vary with contextual factors.

The gap in synthesis relating to the impacts of natural disturbances on soil fauna is obvious. What is less obvious are the reasons for its existence. It is possible that there has been a predominant focus on aboveground rather than belowground organisms, despite the presence of suitable primary studies. It is also possible that there is a lack of primary studies which are available to synthesise. Without a broad overview of the literature on natural disturbances it is unclear which of these is the major reason for a lack of quantitative synthesis on the topic. As such this protocol details the methods of a systematic map to characterize the literature relating to the impacts of natural disturbances on soil fauna. This overview will help to identify knowledge clusters where synthesis can be used to summarise findings, and gaps where further primary research is needed.

Objective of the review

Our primary aim is to characterise the primary literature on the effects of different natural disturbances (drought, high rainfall, wind, fire, pests, pathogens) on soil fauna in forest ecosystems. For the purposes of this review we use a broad definition of forest as any area dominated by trees, including naturally occurring and planted forests. Our review will address the following questions:

1. What are the knowledge clusters and gaps relating to the impact of natural disturbances on the abundance, biomass, diversity, and network interactions of soil fauna in forests?
2. Which knowledge clusters are suitable for quantitative synthesis?
3. Which knowledge gaps warrant further primary studies being undertaken?

Question components

We are interested in studies that assessed the impacts of natural disturbances on soil biodiversity in forest ecosystems in field settings. As such, we define five important elements that guide the scope of our systematic map: Population, Exposure, Comparison, Outcomes, Space (PECOS) following Grames et al (2019).

Population: We will include studies of soil fauna found in forest ecosystems. However, defining what constitutes soil fauna is not simple (Nielsen 2019; Gongalsky 2021; Orgiazzi 2021). For the purposes of this study we define soil fauna as invertebrates which spend a significant proportion of their life in litter and/or soil, excluding ants. We chose to exclude ants for two reasons. Firstly there have been a number of recent syntheses on the impact of natural disturbances on this group (Vasconcelos, Maravalhas & Cornelissen 2017; Andersen 2019). Secondly, inclusion of search terms relating to this group dramatically increased the number of articles we identified during the scoping of search terms. Details of the taxonomic groups we will include are given in Table 1.

Exposure: We are interested in studies that investigate the impacts of different natural disturbances, including drought/reductions in precipitation, increases in rainfall, insect pests, plant pathogens, fire, and windthrow. For the purposes of this study we will not place any threshold on the intensity of disturbance that needs to be met to allow inclusion. As such, if a study reports that it studied the impacts of drought, or any of the disturbances we consider to be relevant exposures, we will consider it to be relevant under this criterion.

Comparison: We are interested in any comparison between forests that vary in the frequency or intensity of disturbance that they are subject to. This comparison may be spatial or temporal.

Outcomes: We are interested in outcomes relating to the abundance, biomass, and diversity of soil fauna. We are also interested in outcomes relating to interactions between different soil fauna.

Space: We are interested only in studies carried out in the field, but will make no restrictions based on the geographic location in which a study is conducted. All types of forest and woodland are included.

Table 1 - Taxonomic groups of soil fauna which we will include in our systematic map. Size classification is based on Nielsen (2019).

Taxonomic group	Common name	Size classification
Nematoda	Nematodes	Microfauna
Protozoa	Protozoans	Microfauna
Protista	Protists	Microfauna
Tardigrada	Tardigrades	Microfauna
Rotifera	Rotifers	Microfauna/Mesofauna
Acari	Mites	Mesofauna
Collembola	Springtails	Mesofauna
Protura	Proturans	Mesofauna
Diplura	Diplurans	Mesofauna
Symphyla	Pseudocentipedes	Mesofauna/macrofauna
Enchytraeidae	Potworms	Mesofauna
Chelonethi	Pseudoscorpions	Mesofauna/macrofauna
Isoptera	Termites	Mesofauna/macrofauna
Isopoda	Isopods	Macrofauna
Opiliones	Harvestman	Macrofauna
Amphipoda	Amphipods	Macrofauna
Chilipoda	Centipedes	Macrofauna/megafauna
Diplopoda	Millipedes	Macrofauna/megafauna
Megadrilacea	Earthworms	Macrofauna/megafauna
Coleoptera	Beetles	Macrofauna/megafauna
Araneida	Spiders	Macrofauna/megafauna
Mollusca	Molluscs	Megafauna

Methods

The methods of this study will follow guidelines for synthesis in environmental management (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018). Throughout the sections relating to manual screening and text extraction, the protocol follows the ROSES standards for systematic maps and reviews (Haddaway *et al.* 2018). We have also completed a ROSES checklist, which is available in Supplementary file 1.

Stakeholder engagement

The topic and research questions were developed as part of the HoliSoils project, which focuses on holistic management practices, modelling, and monitoring for European forest soils. The topic was defined in a series of meetings with researchers who form the HoliSoils consortium and feedback via email on proposed topics. Following this, a series of questions were proposed and feedback from consortium members was included. As a result of these meetings a review team (the authors of this protocol) was defined who will guide the development of synthesis during the project. During scoping of the project searches that included soil microbes as a population of interest indicated that their inclusion would produce a very large literature that was estimated to require over 6 months to screen and extract data from (Haddaway & Westgate 2019). As a result of this and because there have already been a large number of syntheses on the impacts of natural disturbances on soil microbes, the review team decided to exclude soil microbes from the systematic map. We will continue to provide feedback to the wider consortium throughout the duration of the project.

Search terms

Our search strategy is designed to retrieve publications on the impacts of the focal disturbances on soil biodiversity in forest ecosystems. To do this we will search for publications in four bibliographic platforms that we have identified as relevant. In addition to published, peer-reviewed literature, we will also search for unpublished research to minimize the risk of publication bias. We will not restrict the search to articles during a particular period of time but will screen all papers produced by searches. The rationale for using multiple databases for our search is that using single bibliographic platforms can lead to studies being missed, potentially leading to unrepresentative samples (Konno & Pullin 2020).

In addition to formal searches, we will accept suggestions for suitable studies from stakeholders that may be interested in the review. We will contact expert researchers in the field to ask for suggestions of studies that might be relevant. We will also identify references from suitable primary studies and reviews that might be useful for our map using the R package citationchaser (Haddaway, Grainger & Gray 2021).

To identify the search terms that we will use for the systematic map, we used the methodology suggested by Grames et al (2019). This involved the identification of 'naive' search terms based on the different PECO elements of our questions and scoping of these terms using the Web of Science and Scopus platforms. We decided to restrict our search terms to those related to the population and exposure elements of our PECO because we were concerned that articles may not give details of the outcome and comparison elements in their titles or abstracts. Once our search terms returned all our benchmark studies (see below) all references were downloaded and duplicates removed using the R package revtools (Westgate 2019). We then used the R package litsearchr to identify potentially useful additional keywords based on those found in the articles during the literature search (Grames, Stillman & Tingley 2019). PM manually reviewed suggested keywords and those considered to be useful were added. Table 2 gives details of the different keywords and associated PECO elements for this study. We then followed the recommendations of Foo et al. (2021) to estimate the number of relevant studies returned by our searches. To do this searched the Web of Science and Scopus platforms and randomly selected 500 of the

returned references. We screened the references against our inclusion criteria to determine the percentage that met our inclusion criteria. Further details of this process can be found in Supplementary file 2. Since different bibliographic platforms and databases have different rules for the formatting of searches, we developed specific searches for each search system. Details of these search terms for each of the four bibliographic platforms can be found in Supplementary file 2.

Table 2 - Terms associated with different PECO elements

PECO element	PECO elements for this study	Search terms related to PECO element
Population	Forest soil fauna	<p>Forest synonyms = Forest, Woodland, Plantation</p> <p>Soil synonyms= Soil, Belowground, Root</p> <p>Soil fauna terms = Soil biodiversity, Belowground biodiversity, Soil diversity, Belowground diversity, Biodiversity, Biota, Fauna, Microfauna, Mesofauna, Macrofauna, Animal, Arthropod, Invertebrate, Detritivore, Macroarthropod, Microarthropod, Protozoa, Ciliate, Nematode, Nematoda, Protist, Rotifer, Rotifera, Tardigrade, Acari, Oribatid, Mite, Collembola, Springtail, Protura, Diplura, Symphyla, Chelonethi, Opiliones, Harvestmen, Ispotera, Termite, Isopoda, Woodlice, Amphipoda, Megadrilacea, Oligochaete, Annelid, Enchytraeus, Enchytraeidae, Potworm, Lumbricidae, Earthworm, Chilopoda, Centipedes, Diplopoda, Millipedes, Coleoptera, Beetles, Araneida, Spiders, Mollusca, Snails, Slugs</p>
Exposures	Drought, Windthrow, Fire, Extreme rainfall, Insect pests, Tree pathogens	Drought, Fire, Wind, Typhoon, Cyclone, Hurricane, Storm, Rain, Precipitation, Disturbance, Global change, Bark beetle, Pest, Insect herbivore, Pathogen

Search languages

We will review publications in English only. We will make a record of all publications that we excluded because they were not in English. We acknowledge that excluding literature written in non-English languages is a shortcoming that may lead to biases (Konno *et al.* 2020; Amano *et al.* 2021). However, we lack the resources needed to work in other languages, especially since checking consistency of inclusion requires dual-screening of articles.

Assessment of search comprehensiveness

To estimate the comprehensiveness of our search the review team developed a benchmark list of articles. These represent articles that we feel our searches must capture in order to be considered comprehensive - as recommended by guidelines for environmental evidence synthesis (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018). We supplemented this list with relevant English-language articles mentioned by reviews and meta-analysis of the impacts of disturbances on belowground organisms and soil conditions (Neary *et al.* 1999; Bouget & Duelli 2004; Blankinship, Niklaus & Hungate 2011; Pressler, Moore & Cotrufo 2019; Kristensen, Rousk & Metcalfe 2020; Zhou, Wang & Luo 2020; Certini *et al.* 2021). Table 3 gives a summary of the benchmark studies.

Platforms to be searched

Scopus and Web of Science searches will use the 'title, keyword, and abstract' and 'topic' functions respectively. Web of Science will be accessed using the subscription offered by the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), which includes: Science Citation Index Expanded, Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science, Social Sciences Citation Index, Emerging Sources Citation Index, Index Chemicus, Book Citation Index - Science, Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Social Science & Humanities, Book Citation Index - Social Science & Humanities, Arts & Humanities Citation Index, and Current Chemical Reactions. Open Access Theses and Dissertations will be searched using the 'any field' option. In addition to specialist bibliographic platforms we will search one web-based search engine, Google Scholar. To assist this we will use the R package gscraper to bulk download the first 1000 relevant references found during searches of Google scholar. Previous work has shown that Google Scholar can be useful for finding both academic and grey literature (Haddaway *et al.* 2015).

All references will be downloaded as .bib or .ris files and revtools used to remove duplicate articles (Westgate 2019). We will then import the full library into Zotero, which we will use to convert the references to an Endnote XML file. We will then upload this xml file to sysrev (Bozada *et al.* 2021) - an online tool that allows for screening and data extraction by review teams. Using sysrev will allow the screening process to be as transparent as possible as it will allow people that are interested in the review to examine decisions about the inclusion/exclusion of studies.

Article Screening and Study eligibility criteria

Screening process

Articles will be screened using sysrev (Bozada *et al.* 2021) using the eligibility criteria detailed below. First, titles will be screened for relevance, followed by abstracts. Articles that meet inclusion criteria or that do not provide enough detail to determine whether they meet inclusion criteria will be retained and their full text reviewed if it is not clear whether they should be included. Full texts will be reviewed offline and metadata recorded in Excel spreadsheets.

Consistency checking

To check for consistency, a random sample of 10% of titles and/or abstracts will be screened by two team members, using our inclusion criteria. Any disagreements between the two

Table 3 - Details of benchmark studies used to assess the comprehensiveness of our search strategy. For more detail see Supplementary file 2.

Reference	Focal taxa	Disturbance(s)
Haimi, Fritze & Moilanen (2000)	Oligochaeta, microarthropoda, collembola, oribatida, mesostigmata	Fire
Čuchta, Miklisová & Kováč (2013)	Collembola	Fire, windthrow
Landesman, Treonis, & Dighton (2011)	Mesofauna	Drought
Kim & Jung (2008)	Microfauna	Fire
Malmström et al (2009)	Mesofauna, macrofauna	Fire
Zaitsev et al (2014)	Macrofauna	Fire
Lindberg et al (2002)	Oribatida, Mesostigmata, Collembola, Macroarthropod predators, Enchytraeidae	Drought, Precipitation increases
Sohlenius and Wasilewska(1984)	Nematoda	Precipitation increases
Wikars & Schimmel (2001)	Soil invertebrates	Fire
Springett (1976)	Mesofauna	Fire
Mirzaei (2016)	Macrofauna	Fire
Santonja et al (2017)	Mesofauna	Drought
Xu et al (2012)	Mesofauna	Drought
Lindberg & Bengtsson (2006)	Mesofauna	Drought
Homet et al (2021)	Mesofauna	Drought
Wehne et al (2021)	Oribatida	Drought, windthrow
Sterzyńska & Skłodowski (2018)	Collembola	Windthrow
Sterzyńska et al (2020)	Protura	Bark beetles
Sun et al (2013)	Nematoda	Precipitation increases
Malmström et al (2008)	Protura, Collembola	Fire

people will be discussed, and eligibility criteria will be revised to show how disagreements were resolved. Kappa scores will be calculated to test the agreement between the two people (Cohen 1960). If Kappa scores are below 0.6, another 10% of titles and/or abstracts were screened by the same two team members. Disagreements will be discussed and resolved again, Kappa scores recalculated, and the consistency checking process repeated until Kappa scores are greater than 0.6. Following this, a sample of 10% of the full texts of publications that meet inclusion criteria based on their titles/abstracts will be screened by two people. This process will mirror that detailed above for title/abstract screening. Members of the review team will not be allowed to make a decision about inclusion of an article that represents a conflict of interest. If review team members encounter an article on which they are a co-author or that is written by a close colleague they will make a note of this conflict of interest and not review the study for inclusion.

Eligibility criteria

To meet our eligibility criteria studies must:

1. Relate to soil fauna in forests
2. Address the impact of an exposure (drought, increases in precipitation, wind, fire, insect herbivores, plant pathogens) of interest
3. Be field-based (i.e. not be carried out in greenhouses or mesocosms)
4. Quantitatively assess soil fauna biomass, abundance, diversity, or trophic interactions in forests
5. Have a comparison between sites that vary in the intensity or frequency of the disturbance that they were exposed to
6. Be written in English

Our eligibility criteria will be applied at three stages: (i) title screening; (ii) abstract screening; (iii) full-text screening. At the title screening stage, to be included titles must mention either a population (soil fauna in forests) or an exposure (drought, increases in precipitation, wind, fire, insect herbivores, plant pathogens) of interest.

At the abstract screening stage, in order to be retained, articles must be likely to meet criteria 1-3 and criterion 5. At the full-text stage criteria 1-6 must be met in order for an article to be retained. Abstract-level and full-text screening are summarised in Figure 1.

At the full-text screening stage, we will provide a reason for the exclusion of all articles that do not meet our inclusion criteria in accordance with ROSES guidelines (Haddaway *et al.* 2018). Reasons may include the inability to find or access the full text of an article, an article not being written in English, lack of PECOS elements, or a failure to take multiple samples for a given time point (Figure 1). We will not perform any critical appraisal of studies as this is considered an optional component of systematic mapping (James, Randall & Haddaway 2016). However, following completion of the systematic map we will carry out critical appraisal of studies for knowledge clusters that we synthesise in follow-up studies. The screening process based on these eligibility criteria is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Summary of screening process at (a) abstract and (b) full text screening stages

Data coding and extraction

Since the aim of this study is to characterise studies of the effects of natural disturbances on soil organisms, we will not extract any details on the impacts of these disturbances, but will focus on extracting metadata. For each study we will extract data on the following variables:

- *Geographic location*: We will record the most detailed location possible, ideally as latitude and longitude. In cases where that is not possible we will record place names. Where studies are undertaken at more than one site we will collect location details for all of these. We will also record the number of sites for each of the studies.
- *Disturbance type*: Studies will be classified as being either studies of drought, fire, windthrow, extreme rainfall, insect outbreaks, or tree pathogens. Where studies have examined more than one disturbance, this will be noted.
- *Taxa*: For studies that examine soil biodiversity details of the taxonomic group(s) examined will be recorded. We will record the taxonomic rank of organisms at the most specific taxonomic level that includes all species in a study.
- *Functional groups*: We will record the size of organisms, divided into the categorical groups macrofauna, mesofauna, and microfauna. We will also classify species by their trophic role as either detritivores, microbivores, herbivores, predators, or omnivores.
- *Outcomes*: For studies that examine soil biodiversity we will identify whether biomass, abundance (measured as density per volume/weight of soil, relative abundance etc), alpha diversity (measured as species density, species richness, diversity indices etc), evenness, or beta and gamma diversity metrics were measured.
- *Study design*: We will record details of the different designs used by studies to assess impacts of disturbances. We will record whether studies are experimental or correlative in nature. For the purposes of this work we will define experimental studies as those in which disturbances were applied by humans in an attempt to simulate natural disturbances. Examples of this include the use of rain exclusion

devices to simulate drought, or experimental burning to simulate wildfires. Correlative studies are those in which this was not the case, in which comparators are defined post-hoc, potentially resulting in biases in counterfactual comparisons (Christie *et al.* 2019, 2020). We will label studies that compared an area where a disturbance occurred with an area where it was not as controlled. Studies that compare between a time prior to a disturbance, and a time during or after a disturbance had occurred will be labelled as a before-and-after studies (Christie *et al.* 2019, 2020). These labels are not mutually exclusive. Where experiments used a blocked design, they will be classified as such, and when correlative studies use paired sites, this will also be recorded. We will also label studies as randomized or not (i.e., where independent samples were randomly allocated to treatment and control groups). We will record the spatio-temporal grain (sampling unit size/duration) and extent (total study area/duration), as well as replication.

- *Sampling methods*: We will collect information on the sampling/extraction methods used in each study. Sampling methods for soil fauna may include soil cores, excavated soil blocks, mustard extraction, Berlese funnel, Baermann funnel and sucrose centrifugation amongst others.
- *Timing of study*: We will record the season in which the study was conducted as it is reported in the study.
- *Duration of study*: We will record the length of time from the first measurement of outcomes to the final measurement of outcomes.
- *Time after disturbance*: We will record the minimum and maximum amount of time after a disturbance at which an outcome was measured as well as the frequency of sampling over time
- *Data availability*: to aid future synthesis we will collect information on the availability of data from studies, including whether species x site data matrices are available.

Study mapping and presentation

We will create figures to summarise characteristics of the dataset, showing the frequency of studies from different regions, different disturbances, focal taxonomic groups, study outcomes, and other relevant characteristics. We will generate heat maps of topics to show their co-occurrence - particularly for different taxonomic groups, disturbances, and outcomes. We will use narrative synthesis to discuss themes in the literature and patterns of data found in the analyses.

Declaration

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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